

Microstructural and magnetic investigations in Co₂FeGa thin films for spintronics applications

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Abstract:

Half-metallic ferromagnets (HFMs) of Heusler type have drawn great interest due to their predicted high spin polarization at the Fermi level (E_F) [1] and their high potential applications in spintronics such as magnetic tunnel junctions (MTJs) in tunnel magneto resistance (TMR) based devices [2]. Among the Co-based Heusler alloys, Co₂FeGa thin films attracted a great interest due to their high temperature stability. Though Co₂FeGa is not a half-metallic ferromagnet from the first principles calculations, it exhibited a significant spin polarization of 59% using point contact Andreev reflection (PCAR) technique which was created a great interest to study this system for spintronics applications. In light of above, a thickness dependent investigation has been carried out in Co₂FeGa thin films expecting to give a great insight to use them for device applications. The role of film thickness on the structural, microstructural and magnetic properties of Co₂FeGa thin films were systematically investigated. The increase in film thickness shows a linear dependence with grain size. A gradual decrease in coercivity (H_c) and almost constant saturation magnetization (M_s) has been observed at room temperature for the films with grain size > 12 nm. Curie temperature (T_C) is found to increase gradually with increase in grain size. The decrease in H_c and increase in T_C are attributed to the increase in grain size. Temperature dependent magnetic hysteresis loops which exhibit nearly a constant M_s value till 873 K for films of thickness > 10 nm, evidences the high temperature stability of Co₂FeGa thin films. The threshold film thickness to exhibit better thermally stable magnetic properties was identified.

Keywords: Spintronics, Co₂FeGa thin film, microstructure, magnetic property.

References:

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